

The Formation of cellular tissue from quail cells around beans and lentils in the cavity between skin and the quail skeleton: New hopes in genetic engineering

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We make a cavity in the body of some quails and put some beans and lentils in it. This cavity was placed between skin and skeleton of quails. Then we covered this cavity or hole by a black glue. After a week, we removed glue and observed that a cellular tissue from quail cells is formed between beans and lentils. This means that by putting plants in body of animals, a connection between cells of plant and animal is formed. This may produce some hopes in genetic engineering.

A quail with a cavity or hole between it's skin and skeleton

Covering the cavity in quail's body by black glue

Picking up package of beans, lentils and cellular tissue which connect them

Considering package of beans, lentils and cellular tissue which connect them